

PHILOSOPHY

THE PLACE OF ADVERTISING IN THE COMMUNICATIVE NEEDS OF THE PERSON OF THE INFORMATION SOCIETY

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Abstract

The realities of human coexistence in the information world are rapidly changing the components of society and require people to take new action for more effective coexistence. Communicative activity generates the main type of change, as it forms a new information world, which consists of a complex system of communications and methods, content, frequency of information exchange, ensuring high efficiency of society, helping to quickly exchange data and exist in the information world. Advertising acts as a communication factor that allows you to manage the efficiency and optimality of the overall communication system. As a result of the formation of the information society, new demands of people from society and vice versa appear, in which the paradigm of survival consists in the information domination of subjects. The main demand of society is the requirement of virtual interaction, human demand – for privacy, and at the same time, information dominance. The virtualized world complements reality with its own attributes, because it solves a number of previously problematic things that hindered rapid social interaction: the speed of information transfer, its targeting, its mass. In the range of concepts there is an understanding of the "media subject" as a person or company, or any other entity that is represented virtually, having a real subject in reality. As a result of active social communication of the "media subject" there is an opportunity to expand the range of influence on the mass consciousness. Information dominance together with advertising provide the ability to obtain social and material benefits, due to the right actions, which is the main purpose of these entities. Advertising is a catalyst for communication processes that meet the information needs of consumers and provide the advertiser with social activity in the information space. Advertising is closely linked to different types of human interaction, which causes its synergistic effect for each of them.

Keywords: communication, information, advertising, society, efficiency, social communication, information domination, society.

The problem of the role of advertising is its nature of use by modern society. As a result of active social interaction, including virtual, subjects must respond quickly to all information challenges and adapt to active competition in society. Advertising, as a catalyst for social activity, benefits the advertiser and partially provides information needs. The social value of advertising lies in its end result - the creation of conditions and provision of social and material benefits. From the human point of view, the dominance of advertising corresponds to the desire of other people to get more social benefits, under the guise of fair, sometimes unfair, competition in society, through technology and information techniques. Accelerated development of advertising around the world, its coverage of more and more human resources, aspects of economics and production have led to the fact that advertising has become a separate type of human activity - the advertising business. The key to its success is high-quality, professional creation of advertising appeals, so that they have the maximum effectiveness of communicative impact on the target audience. This is the basis of creative advertising - an activity that combines creativity and pragmatism. It covers all stages, from the development of an advertising idea to its practical implementation. Advertising is an integral part of public life, as it is a catalyst for social interaction, and a way to gain information dominance in the infosphere.

The aim of the article is to study and analyze the place of advertising, which will help to better understand the stage of development of modern communications (in the advertising section), human needs in the information world, and explore the social factor in communication processes of society.

To write the article, works related to the theory of research in advertising, social philosophy, the theory of mass communication, philosophical understanding of the phenomenon of communication, etc. were studied. These problems were studied by world scientists Florida L., Rascao H., Gonzalez O., Soldevila G., and domestic - Vachevsky M., Golub IM, Dridze TM, Kozlovsky VI, Lisina MI., Makusheva ON, Malimon VI, Mironov Yu. B., Sorokina GV, Musician VL On the basis of these works and examples of modern information space, a study of this topic was carried out.

Let's define the concept of "advertising", "communicative needs". Advertising - one of the forms of mass communication; any paid form of controlled influence carried out through the media in the presentation and use of goods or services [14, p. 390]. The concept of "communicative need", namely, the need for communication was described by MI Lisina, "the need for communication (communication) is the desire to know and appreciate other people, and through them and with their help - to self-knowledge and self-esteem" [13]. The communicative need is based on two others: organic needs and new experiences.

In the realities of modern life, advertising has become almost paramount, becoming a product of culture, as if a mirror of it, reflecting the traditions, beliefs and values of people in modern changing realities. Active social transformations require new ways of interaction between parts of society, which creates a demand for individual efficiency and socialization. Thanks to the latest technologies and methods of communication, there is a way to conduct activities in the infosphere, as a consumer or creator, providing your own or collective demand for resources. It would not be an exaggeration or outright misunderstanding to say that today's society is increasingly characterized by a digital unit where new information and communication technologies (ICTs) have a constant daily impact, configuring themselves as intermediaries of social relations, economy and even knowledge production / dissemination. The scientific approach to the study of advertising requires consideration of advertising as a form of human communication. Forming a relationship, trying to establish channels of communication between the advertiser and his audience is its essence. The effectiveness of advertising influence is due to the specific socio-cultural features of the society in which the process of advertising communication is developing, such as traditions, mentality.

Otherwise, advertising is perceived formally as an accumulation of diverse and numerous advertising media and channels of their transmission. With this approach, advertising is ineffective in practice. The process of communication implements the most common tasks, such as informing about events and facts of public life, developing contacts between people, managing the communication process.

The interaction of society and advertising is a two-fold process: society develops and intensifies advertising, and advertising technologies, in turn, give the appropriate impetus to socio-economic development of society [17, p. 686]. It is also responsible for structuring a new environment in which people interact with each other, with machines, and finally, in which machines interact with each other, sometimes without the active presence of the individual. This "new" environment is called the infosphere [3]. Due to the technical capabilities and methods of information transfer, modern man is able to communicate and meet information needs without the lively participation of other individuals, which gives a new impetus to the development of communication technologies. At the same time, it transforms a person, as new types of interaction with the world are acquired, which create a new environment for existence.

According to social demand, what exists in society: phenomenon, product, cultural, economic, ideological features, have social confirmation. Therefore, advertising is a socially affirmed activity that meets the needs of man and society. From the human point of view, advertising manifests itself as an act of meeting information needs, or finding potential ways to meet them, and a potential solution to problems.

The main function of the individual, as we know, is to ensure - through involvement in culture, inclusion

in social interaction - the ability to communicate, establish communication (exchange of information) with other people and with himself. That is, it must function as an individual subject of communication in the modern socio-cultural space. [12, p.143].

The communicative orientation of the individual, as a motivational prerequisite for communication, implies a stable dominance of communicative needs. If a person's focus on communication prevails among all other needs (self, activity), this is a positive motivating factor for successful psycho-correctional work. A person who strives to maintain good relations with others and focuses on joint activities, his energy, pace will be able to achieve more than one who resists social influences. An important motivating factor is the formation of communicative needs. Needs motivate to come into contact with other people [15, p.9].

According to the subjective turnover of advertising, meeting the demand for information and the potential for dominance in society is a factor in the existence of advertising as a phenomenon in society. However, the place of advertising in various aspects of society is optimal in its own way, because the subjectivity of perception determines its nature. In mass terms, advertising is understood as one of the types of communication, interaction between elements of society.

The phenomenon of advertising should be divided into different understandings, because advertising can act as a cultural phenomenon, a social phenomenon, as a business, or even an art form. With the advent of the information world, man has shifted the desire to dominate not only in the real world, but here. The principle of advertising is associated with the unifying factor of communication, for greater public synergy around their own interests. A person's access to technical means and access to the global network provides an opportunity to apply similar principles in the virtual world.

In terms of the extent of the phenomenon, we must note that advertising at the present stage has become an independent human activity - the advertising business, which together in terms of capitalization is next to the largest human global industries. The key to its success, like any other activity, is quality, professional management and the nature of its origin.

Advertising - one of the most notable phenomena of modern society, and therefore it is natural that it attracts the attention of representatives of various research areas. At the core of advertising is perceived as derived from market relations - as a market-based process of informational impact on the target audience in order to increase sales, increase the prestige of the company and form a positive attitude towards the company and products. Of particular importance is the consideration of advertising as a form of communication between advertisers and consumers, which disseminates information about goods and services through both traditional media and specialized advertising channels. The study of the peculiarities of the process of advertising communication, theoretical and practical aspects of advertising are the fundamental basis for the management of advertising and information activities [18].

The purpose of advertising - to attract attention, interest, convey information to consumers and force

them to act in a certain way, increase demand for goods, maintain or increase market share and ensure effective operation of the enterprise, as well as form a positive image of the product or company [6, p. 27]. Advertising in the system of mass social communication performs several tasks, the main of which are: information, persuasion, reminders, creating additional usefulness that affects people's perception.

At all stages of the creation of advertising communications it is necessary to take into account the socio-cultural determinants of the host party. Without understanding the deep socio-psychological foundations of a kind of socio-cultural code, fixed in the historical memory of the people and reflected in culture in the form of traditions, mental archetypes, socio-cultural norms. Due to the formed functional structure of advertising, an extensive network of means of its creation and mass distribution, modern advertising is increasingly integrated into socio-cultural processes, becoming an integral part of everyday culture.

Advertising communication fulfills the task of satisfying the interests of consumers, forms and consolidates social groups, forms the social experience of society, thus performing one of the most important functions of culture - socio-cultural integration. Advertising communication is a special tool of socio-cultural formation of preferences, standards, which determines the norms and styles of social behavior of people, as well as essentially affects the value-semantic aspects of their social life, including aesthetic, artistic and creative preferences [10].

Under the influence of a large number of cultural, historical, economic and political processes in society, advertising captures all social changes and responds immediately to them, changing internally and generating new modified forms, manifestations, widely recommended cultural images and norms of social prestige. That is why such communication is similar to short-term impact on subjects, as we can see in personal communication and, for the most part, has no long-term impact.

Each advertisement chooses a unique means of influencing the subject so that he can understand advertising, not make one-time purchases or acts of consumption of advertising, but become a regular customer. Therefore, advertising is the only element of marketing, which is to consolidate the impact on the human mind. Thanks to the naturalistic approach, advertising allows the consumer to choose the right search area, as well as help him choose [2]. This allows us to distinguish it as a cultural, informational, communicative phenomenon. In the mass manifestation of the advertising system is a way of imposing or real manifestation of needs and types of their satisfaction. It is communication that is the unifying factor of activity around the chosen ways of influencing people. Thanks to advertising, we can get used to various aspects: product analysis, market analysis, analysis of media opportunities. But the main thing is to observe the characteristics of the product and create the necessary impressions about it. Advertising is also seen as part of the informative power of marketing communications. Due to psy-

chological factors in the flow of advertising, they explain the problems with the new product, reviews, the price of high service life, the buyer respects the product [16, p. 56].

Advertisers are increasingly turning to the needs and qualities of the individual related to his social self-realization. To do this, modern advertising, located in the marginal field of culture, where the most decisive and radical cultural experiments actually take place, had to learn postmodern methods of creating something new from what had already been created before. Once and for all, renouncing its claim to a place among the higher arts, advertising gained self-sufficiency and freedom for bold experiments. It would seem that under these conditions, the classical laws of organization of creative activity, the painful search for a new creative idea, individual and personal aspects of the creative process should have disappeared or at least acquired some new quality. However, this did not happen. The very laws of the creative process have remained unchanged [10].

All the circumstances of the functioning of advertising as an independent cultural form have changed, and dramatically. Its importance today as a socio-cultural phenomenon has changed - in public relations, advertising occupies its own niche as an informant, a regulator of social interaction, only a special case of which is marketing activities. From the point of view of commercial function, of course, the main task of advertising - sales. Also in society, approaches to the evaluation of advertising as a special aesthetic phenomenon are changing. Today, the idea of the artistic merits of the advertising product is quite acceptable, and yet recently such an assessment was considered absurd.

Advertising communication, more than other types of communication, tries to overcome the limitations of existing symbolic forms of communication. In particular, there is a decrease in the share of verbal communications in advertising. Language, this second signaling system, is a means of transmitting meaning rather than meaning. It is not intended, not adapted to the transmission of emotional and other mental states. Advertising tries to create its own language, often using such means of conveying emotions as music, color, smells, but the use of this language is limited by the technical features of mass communication. As a rule, the encrypted message transmitted through one or another communication channel is not perceived by the senses, which are more able to transmit the irrational.

Thus, the rationalization of irrational needs through advertising is determined not only by objectivity, rationality of goods offered for consumption, but also the rationality of the nature of mass communication: the means of transmitting advertising messages are more able to convey logical (semantic) aspects of communication. Advertising, on the one hand, should present the product as a response to unconscious desires and needs that meet the irrational motives of human behavior, ie best suited to his individual world, on the other, its massive nature, the need to be accessible to large masses, make it sufficiently rationalized and formalized.

Special attention is paid to the opinion of sociologist TM Dridze, who considers social communication as a textual activity, ie as an exchange of actions of generation and interpretation of texts. It studies the place and role of texts - messages as communicative-cognitive units in motivated and purposeful (deliberate) exchange of ideas and emotions, attitudes and values, patterns of behavior and activities in the process of socio-cultural communication [8, p.1].

Advertising in a sense perfectly embodies the modern ideal of human cognitive activity, because it is based primarily on knowledge, needs, interests, thinking and imagination of the mass consumer, his inclinations, small and large weaknesses, his strengths and values. She is sincerely concerned with penetrating as deeply as possible into the inner world of man and as directly as possible to ignite his own interests, which he himself should never properly study and appreciate. Massive multipolar broadcasting and individual interpretation of information has led to a powerful communication mechanism for emotionally managing the needs of society and shaping its values. Advertising campaigns that fit the cultural emotional model usually seek trust and closeness to build a relationship and thus be more credible and effective [1]. Turning to the basic activities of man, there is a constant need for information that allows you to learn about the world around you, for effective existence, increase survival, and so on. Advertising, claiming the role of a leader in the information world takes on the function of information. As a result, the price for the correct, from the point of view of the interested person, information becomes valuable. Advertising works on different parameters of consumer confidence and believes that advertisers are constantly improving their strategies to improve their brand image, to make statements plausible, offering consumers something new and fresh [2]. As a result, people show varying degrees of trust in advertising, which determines its effectiveness.

The general requirements to the participants of the creative process remain unchanged and relevant, regardless of the problem to which it is directed, during which the advertising product is created. The techniques are based on understanding the needs of man, for his interest. Importantly:

- to support the constant change in the structure of external information and internal ideas about the advertised product, socio-cultural and socio-psychological context of the advertising campaign through the formation of analogies and the connection of conceptual gaps;

- it is necessary to strive for constant reformulation of the problem, looking for unknown aspects;

- be able to apply existing knowledge, memories and images to create new and apply old knowledge and skills in a new way;

- to look for metaphorical solutions to the problem, using for this purpose non-verbal models of thinking, author's moves, non-standard approaches, etc. The principle - a bold idea and a terrific technique, should be a mainstay for advertising;

- to maintain the internal tension of the creative process, which can arise in three ways "in the conflict

between the traditional and the new at every step of the creative process; in the ideas themselves, in different ways of solving them or the intended products; it can be created between the chaos of uncertainty and the desire to move to a higher level of organization and efficiency within the individual or society. Probably, all three types of tension arise at different stages of the creative process "[9, p. 204].

No less important is the place of advertising in communication needs, when a person acts as a creator. According to her requests, she translates into society her own motives, turned into psychological, visual, abstract layers of understanding. However, communication does not go unilaterally, because the result of society's reactions are reactions to the individual and his object of advertising. When creativity becomes the essence of the human profession, then it, as a creator, first commits itself to society. And their fulfillment or non-fulfillment becomes a criterion for assessing his personality. A good artist must be endowed with the ability to create "productive metaphors", because the basis of creativity in advertising is still the ability to go beyond stereotypical associations, to work with a wide semantic field of cultural meanings.

Today, many authors focus on the perceived and unconscious effects of the advertiser on the consumer, and detail the difference between rational actions based on logic and persuasive arguments, and irrational actions based on emotions and feelings. The effects vary in shape and intensity. The simplest and most common form, perhaps, can be considered social facilitation - the presence of other people at the time when a person performs certain actions, and the most difficult are the many types of hypnosis, the psychological mechanisms of which are still poorly understood.

The problem of psychological influences (social influences) in the psychology of advertising as a field of scientific knowledge is extremely relevant also because it is associated with a number of ethical issues. After all, any influence involves a change in human consciousness, an obstacle to freedom of choice. Many authors believe that we are all completely dependent on each other, and there is no completely free choice, even mental, at all. However, "what advertising really sells is a means of placing oneself in front of the world." In other words, advertising, outside the commercial framework, sells "philosophy of life" and "representation of ideal ethnic universes" [5]. Philosophy provides an opportunity to analyze the phenomenon of advertising from different aspects of human and social life, to compare the phenomenon with man and vice versa. Therefore, from this point of view, the advertising message is a way to insert the individual into an imaginary ideal situation, where a certain need in the real world is solved. It is interpretation that plays a crucial role in the process of human communication.

The question still remains: why and in what cases do people still buy goods that they do not really need? That is why the problem of studying the effectiveness of methods of psychological influence in advertising, as well as the relationship between influence and needs, today is considered the main problem of understanding

advertising. Social philosophy gives us an understanding of the imperfections of man, so in existence man seeks to fill internal problems with various mental attitudes that produce appropriate actions. Due to the oversaturation of information in the modern information field and successful psychological techniques, some advertisers are able to inspire faith to buy anything that will solve internal problems. Thus, the mass audience of imperfect, and this is almost all, people are potentially unstable to powerful advertising influence. Advertising uses a large number of different ways, methods, techniques of social influence, psychological influence and manipulation. In particular, various forms of hypnosis, suggestion, imitation, infection, beliefs, socio-psychological attitudes. In particular, in adults man.

Thanks to art, advertising communication is able to target any audience. The idea of an artistic product reaches the audience. It is enriched by the artist's experience, initially invariant, because it generates mutual ideas in people's minds. Art provokes actions and purposefully, forcing viewers to think. And the more significant the guiding idea in the product, the more significant are the ideas that arise in the audience [14, p. 390]. Thus, if the guiding idea inherent in a work of art is organically combined with the basic idea of social development, which is especially important in social advertising, revealing all the best that has been accumulated by mankind, the personal mission of the artist is fulfilled.

Advertising communication, which covers all aspects of cultural space, seeks to master the diversity of spiritual and creative forces of man. At the same time, she herself becomes a moderator of creativity far beyond the advertising product she created - in the space of human actions and deeds, a person's attitude to things, relationships with other people. After all, almost every human action "is not only a technical operation on a thing, but also an action on another person, which expresses the attitude to it ... existential" [14, p. 390].

The new paradigm of creativity that is emerging today is opposed to the classic one, built on the author-society dilemma. Many creative people, inspired by the "cult of creativity and the myths of proudly self-sufficient creative individuality and divine talent," are not interested in approving it. They are not ready to accept a paradigm that destroys the existing hierarchy and renounces the privileged position of the creator-prophet, though not always heard, but always exclusive, unique and special.

Therefore, in the context of the analysis of the cultural system of advertising communication, we highlight several important characteristics of creativity: creativity is manifested in the ability of the advertiser to respond adaptively to the need for new approaches and new products. This ability also allows you to realize new things in life and culture (this process itself can be both conscious and unconscious); formation of creative result in advertising communication, it is provided by the personal potential of the creator, the strength of his internal motivation to create a new creative product; specific properties of the creative process, product and personality are their originality, consistency, validity, adequacy to solve the problem, the implementation of

the necessary aesthetic, ideological, economic, environmental qualities in the advertising product, choosing the optimal form, correctness and original at the moment; creative products in advertising communication can be very different in nature, but they can all be divided into creative results achieved by authors-craters, and results obtained by other subjects of advertising communication in the process of perception of the advertising product [7, p. 21].

Advertising communication performs the functions of satisfying the interests of consumers, forms the social experience of society, thus performing one of the most important functions of culture - socio-cultural integration. Advertising communication is a special tool for socio-cultural formation of preferences, standards, norms and styles of social behavior, as well as a significant impact on the value and semantic aspects of their social life, including aesthetic, artistic and creative preferences [10].

In the conditions of development of market economy in Ukraine of its adequate infrastructure, advertising acquires important socio-economic value. The advertising market today is an important area of the national economy, the main source of funding for the media, one of the components of cultural life. In addition, the advertising market is part of the information system of society, and information and technology to influence the mass consciousness are today one of the key factors in the development of the social system.

Conclusion. The place of advertising in human communication needs is an important factor in human information activity. A person, as a consumer, needs advertising content to better understand the successful solution of problems and obtain social or material benefits, using the communicative factor. Man, as a creator, needs communicative action with others for the social recognition of their own actions or goods through the prism of public opinion. The ability to communicate arises from the moment it is motivated by one of the parties to the communication. Advertising has reached a global scale, due to the need for rapid exchange of information and the establishment of economic relations. In terms of the extent of the phenomenon, we must note that advertising at the present stage has become an independent human activity - the advertising business, which together in terms of capitalization is next to the largest human global industries. That is why the need for people to compete for material or social benefits is a catalyst for the use of advertising in society, even globally. The desire for dominance is a factor in the use of any advertising techniques, both honest and dishonest, but in civilized countries there are certain regulators that regulate this area from excessive, unethical, harmful influences. Advertising is a catalyst for communication processes that meet the information needs of consumers and provide the advertiser with social activity in the information space. Advertising is closely linked to different types of human interaction, which causes its synergistic effect for each of them and is mutually beneficial for all parties involved.

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